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FORMATION OF ENGINEERING AND PEDAGOGICAL SPECIALITIES STUDENTS PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN THE CONTEXT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Abstract

The article deals with the foreign language professional competence of students in the process of learning a foreign language for professional purposes. The national and European experience of diagnosing students' foreign language professional competence in the context of learning a foreign language for professional purposes is considered. The professional competence of students is analyzed in detail. The theoretical and methodological aspects of diagnosing students' foreign language professional competence in the context of learning a foreign language for professional purposes are highlighted.

Keywords: *diagnostics, foreign language professional competence, foreign language learning process, professional orientation.*

Ukraine's orientation towards joining the European community implies certain requirements for specialists in all fields, one of which is fluency in foreign languages. Expansion of international cooperation contacts, attraction of foreign investments, creation of new joint ventures, etc. requires modernization of modern education, first of all, introduction of the professional competence approach into the educational paradigm, which will provide students with theoretical knowledge, practical skills, personal and professional development [1].

Nowadays, professional foreign language proficiency and the ability to communicate in business and science are prerequisites for successful career development of engineering and pedagogical graduates.

The problems of the essence of basic competences and their formation in future specialists have been studied by many scholars. However, despite the large number of scientific works on theoretical and practical aspects of diagnosing students' foreign language professional competence in the process of learning a foreign language for professional purposes, some important aspects remain unresolved, namely the definition of the concept of foreign language professional competence remains controversial.

The purpose of the article is to carry out a theoretical analysis and empirical study of the foreign language professional competence of engineering and pedagogical specialties students in the context of learning a foreign language for professional purposes.

At the present stage of society development in general and education in particular, personal competence is extremely relevant and important for personal self-realization. The use of the term competence at the state level, as well as its consolidation in official documents, indicates that the process of forming and developing the competences of students is a priority for the functioning of the education system.

One of the components of the academic competence of students of engineering and pedagogical specialties is knowledge of foreign languages, which allows students to work with various educational and scientific sources, reference books, professional information, etc.; conduct business correspondence, work effectively with a computer, find information on the Internet, libraries of foreign universities, databases of scientific papers, make presentations in Power Point mode, communicate with colleagues from abroad, gain new knowledge through knowledge of a foreign language, etc. Knowledge of foreign languages plays a significant role in shaping the professional competence of graduates of non-language specialties. However, it should be borne in mind that professional competence is not a stable value: it is constantly changing under the influence of external factors, scientific and technological progress, etc. There is no established list of competences, as each profession has a unique set of abilities peculiar to it, without mastering which the process of adaptation and further professional performance of their duties can cause significant problems.

Studying foreign languages on the basis of professional orientation helps to develop the skills of a future specialist to realize themselves in communication, establish business contacts, study foreign sources, analyze modern scientific achievements, improve skills and present ideas to the professional community. Professional communication competence develops such professional qualities as independence, self-control, responsibility, creative thinking and professionalism. Professional-oriented foreign language teaching involves teaching a foreign language to students in the modern context of the peculiarities of their future profession. Of course, this approach should take into account the personal qualities of students. A skillful combination of professional and linguistic knowledge and skills will help graduates of engineering and pedagogical specialties to achieve a level of professionally ori-

ented communicative competence in a foreign language, which will allow them to use a foreign language in their professional activities at the level of international standards. In view of the high requirements for graduates of engineering and pedagogical specialties in terms of professional and practical knowledge of foreign languages, the development of organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for teaching students foreign languages for their further use for professional purposes is becoming relevant. The general theoretical knowledge gained by students while studying at a higher education institution will be effective and significant when combined with professional practice. Therefore, in the learning process, it is necessary to implement the objectives of the discipline, take into account the interests and motivation of students. The teacher should select the educational material in such a way that its professional specificity and students' language competence work to meet future professional needs. Comprehensive mastery of general and professional (aimed at practical professional activity) components will contribute to the full and successful implementation of tasks and goals.

The professional orientation of the activity requires integration of the discipline 'Foreign Language' with the specialized disciplines; it sets the task for the foreign language teacher to teach the future specialist to use a foreign language on the basis of interdisciplinary connections as a means of systematically replenishing their professional knowledge and as a way of developing professional skills; it involves the use of forms and methods of teaching that ensure the formation of the necessary professional skills of the future specialist [2]. One of the main conditions for teaching a professional foreign language is the interaction of teachers of the language and specialized departments at all stages of education, including joint learning. Communicative competence primarily involves the acquisition of lexical competence, without which full communication is impossible. Teachers of higher education institutions, researchers, and methodologists study the role of lexical mechanisms in receptive and productive speech activities, develop types of exercises, and compile minimum dictionaries of professional vocabulary. However, an effective solution to this problem is possible only if such work is constantly improved, new methods of teaching professional vocabulary to engineering and pedagogical students are searched for and implemented. The analysis of the problem of determining the stages of foreign language lexical competence formation is based on the position that the process of mastering foreign language vocabulary begins with the acquisition of knowledge about vocabulary and the formation of primary (lexical) skills and ends with the development of secondary (speech) skills.

One of the organizational and pedagogical factors that encourages students to engage in professional ac-

tivities and positively influences their desire to be fluent in a foreign language is the modelling of professionally oriented situations. This approach involves the selection of productive methods of organizing the educational process, taking into account the personal qualities of students, their interests and plans for the future [3].

The analysis of scientific sources and the actual problem of training students of engineering and pedagogical specialties for future professional activities allows us to conclude that the formation of professional foreign language communicative competence of students of engineering and pedagogical specialties requires compliance with the goals and plans of training, namely the training system should be aimed at meeting practical needs; training of future specialists is comprehensive, theoretical and practical.

The basis of effective foreign language teaching should be interdisciplinary interaction of teachers and close interconnection between the content and approaches to teaching general theoretical, professional disciplines and the discipline of a foreign language for professional and business communication. In active work, guided by the teacher, students acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities for professional activities, develop their creative abilities, etc.

One of the organizational and pedagogical factors that encourages students to engage in professional activities and positively influences their desire to be fluent in a foreign language is the modelling of professionally oriented situations. This approach involves the selection of productive methods of organizing the educational process, taking into account the personal qualities of students, their interests and plans for the future.

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